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Consolidated status assessment report for 6 CDIs

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Glossary

Abbreviation	Full official name (original language, <i>English translation as needed</i>)
AP	Academic Partner
BIOS	BioSens Institut Istraživačko – razvojni institut za informacione tehnologije biosistema (<i>BioSense Institute – Research and Development Institute for Information Technologies in Biosystems</i>)
CDI	Change-driven initiative
DELTA	Delta Fondacija (<i>Delta Foundation</i>)
DIL	Deutsches Institut für Lebensmitteltechnik e.V. (<i>German Institute of Food Technology</i>)
EC	European Commission
ECSA	Verein der Europäischen Bürgerwissenschaften (<i>European Citizen Science Association</i>)
ERA	European Research Area
ERS	Ernährungsrat StadtRegion Stuttgart e.V. (<i>Food Policy Council City Region Stuttgart registered association</i>)
FG	Focus Group
IAAC	Institut d'Arquitectura Avançada de Catalunya (<i>Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia</i>)
ibid.	ibidem (<i>In the same place</i>)
i.e.	id est (<i>That is</i>)
IrsiCaixa	Fundacio Privada Institut de Recerca de la Sida-Caixa (<i>Private Foundation for AIDS Research Institute, IrsiCaixa</i>)
IRTA	Institut de Recerca i Tecnologia Agroalimentàries (<i>Institute of Agrifood Research and Technology</i>)
KIS	Kisléptékű Termékelőállítók és Szolgáltatók Országos Érdekképviselőinek Egyesülete (<i>National Association of Interest Representations for Small-scale Producers and Service Providers</i>)
PLP	Pannon Helyi Termék Nonprofit Kft. (<i>Pannonian Local Products Nonprofit Ltd.</i>)
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
TcV	Stichting Transitiecoalitie Voedsel (<i>The Food Transition Coalition Foundation</i>)
UHOH	Universität Hohenheim (<i>University of Hohenheim</i>)
UOXF	The Chancellor, Masters and Scholars of the University of Oxford
VU	Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (<i>Free University of Amsterdam</i>)
WP	Work Package
WUR	Wageningen University & Research

Executive Summary

This report is part of a European Union funded project, namely, “Fostering food system transformation by integrating heterogeneous perspectives in knowledge and innovation within the ERA” (FOSTER, Grant Agreement No. 101059954). The FOSTER project aims to contribute to changing the scientific knowledge base and the associated knowledge and innovation system in support of food system transformation towards sustainability. To this end, the FOSTER project collaborates closely with six change-driven initiatives (CDIs) from across the food systems, which are based in five countries across Europe: Fab Lab Barcelona as part of the Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia (Fab Lab IAAC - Spain), Living Lab for Health - as part of the Research Institute IrsiCaixa (Living Lab IrsiCaixa - Spain), the Food Policy Council Stuttgart (ERS - Germany), Delta Foundation (DELTA - Serbia) with the local initiative called “Digital Village,” Pannonian Local Products Nonprofit Ltd. (PLP - Hungary), and the Food Transition Coalition (TcV – the Netherlands).

The aim of this report is to provide a baseline assessment for these CDIs, by sharing insights from each CDI with respect to their ambitions, their theories of change, and their activities. Additionally, the CDIs’ target stakeholder groups and interactions with the Knowledge & Innovation system are examined. In order to answer the objectives of the report, several data sources have been drawn upon, including notes from the project kick-off meeting, and results of a survey initiated by the University of Hohenheim and the University of Oxford. Additionally, focus group discussion sessions between academic partners (APs) and CDIs, as well as additional interactions via semi-structured interviews and follow-up correspondence with the CDIs are used as data sources for this report.

Each of the six CDIs works directly in the food system and employs a diversity of engagement strategies. For example, ERS, Living Lab IrsiCaixa, and Fab Lab Barcelona share similar ambitions of being a type of platform, where stakeholders may work on their own projects. ERS unites experts and stakeholders to create a sustainable food strategy for the city of Stuttgart. Fab Lab Barcelona creates space for their course participants to co-design food production and food processing solutions. PLP holds the aim of preserving traditions and supporting local production and consumption by providing advisory support for the interested actors as well as new mechanisms for selling their products. TcV uses the approach of being a connector, i.e., bringing different stakeholders and changemakers together in order to co-create policy suggestions. The activities as part of “Digital Village” (Delta Foundation) are linked to modernization and digital agriculture and are focused on one stakeholder group, i.e., local farmers, by spreading expert knowledge and supporting farmers in the use of digital technology. Living Lab IrsiCaixa works on collective impact through diverse participatory strategies. The CDIs thus bring a great deal of combined theoretical and practical knowledge in food system transformation.

Chapter 1

Introduction

Chapter 1 - Introduction

FOSTER narrative

The FOSTER project was set up to “build a foundation from which a Knowledge and Innovation (K&I) governance structure for Europe’s food system can emerge” (FOSTER, 2023). In FOSTER, we work on how to change, improve, and broaden the scientific knowledge base and the associated knowledge and innovation system (in and for the food system). Food system conceptualization in FOSTER is based on the system visualization from the project Foresight4Food, but extended with added drivers, e.g., Resources and Energy, Health, and Mobility. In FOSTER, we expect that by changing how knowledge is produced (by scientists, by people engaged across the food sector etc.) and used (amongst others, by policy makers, scientists, farmers and other food system actors), this will serve as a lever to change how our food is produced, processed, distributed, consumed and its waste is discarded or re-used towards a more sustainable and just system. For this reason, the following report provides the baseline assessment across six change-driven initiatives (CDIs), who are collaborators and partners of the FOSTER project and who present diverse contributions in knowledge production in the food system from a very practical side.

1.1 Background

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a baseline assessment of the change-driven initiatives (CDIs, see chapter 3.1. regarding the terminology, at the start of the FOSTER project. Each CDI works in tandem with an academic partner (AP), who act as translators between CDIs and the formal academic system, as well as facilitators during the knowledge co-production process. This deliverable was developed under the lead of the University of Hohenheim (UHOH) and in close cooperation with the CDIs as well as the APs and the Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam (VU).

The aim of this baseline assessment is:

1. To understand the CDIs’ ambitions, their theories of change and their activities (i.e., how CDIs want to achieve their ambitions),
2. To examine their target stakeholder groups, and their embedding in networks,
3. To understand relevant knowledge sources, how CDIs access knowledge and interact with the K&I system.

This baseline assessment then builds the basis for the needs and gaps assessment in Task 3.2 (T3.2), as well as input for the summer schools in Work Package 2 (WP2). During the process, both Spanish CDI partners are assessed separately similarly as done by other CDI partners, in order to bring in both of their strengths and perspectives on the food system separately. For the preliminary assessment it is crucial to look at both CDIs on their own to better understand each organisation in depth.

The following report includes three main sections: methodology (chapter 1.2), summaries of each respective CDI (chapter 2), and synthesis across the six CDIs (chapter 3).

1.2 Methodology

In order to fulfil the goals of the assessment, several data collection methods were employed. The initial plan was to perform interviews with a representative from each CDI. After reflecting on the possibly limited perspective resulting from such interviews with a single individual holding a single viewpoint, the WP3 members in consultation with the project Steering Group agreed to establish focus group (FG) sessions between APs and representatives of the respective CDI, with the expectation that hearing multiple perspectives would generate a more rounded understanding for the APs, potentially stimulate discussion within the CDIs themselves, and create an opportunity for the APs and the CDIs to deepen their relationship within the FOSTER collaboration. Besides the FG sessions, project kick-off notes, interviews with CDI representatives, and preliminary survey data as well as the direct input of the CDIs are used as data sources for the analysis.

Kick-off notes, interviews and survey, web-resources

During the project kick-off event on 20th-21st of September (2023) in Brussels (Belgium), several agenda points (Appendix 1) were made for gaining the first insight from the respective partners. Notes were taken along the meeting by several research partners and shared among the consortium members. In the report, the reference source from the kick-off event will be noted as: kick-off notes.

Additionally, in the first months of the project, WP3 leads in cooperation with University of Oxford (UOXF) initiated a survey which asked the CDIs for information on the following questions: the history, formal objective, management structure, stakeholder engagement etc. The purpose of this survey was to understand the basic structure of the respective CDIs (see Appendix 2 for a full list of questions covered in the survey). The information coming from this data source will be identified as: survey.

Meanwhile, consortium members from the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) and VU organized semi-structured interviews with CDIs in order to follow up on the discussion points raised during the kick-off event. The main questions involved aspects of the CDIs' missions and ambitions, as well as the CDIs' current stakeholder networks. Except for the CDI partner in Hungary, these interviews were held virtually and recorded. The transcripts and short summaries were created by the researchers of VU. In the case of Hungary, the members of Pannonian Local Products Ltd. (PLP) answered the key interview questions in a written format. In the text, the reference source from the online semi-structured interviews will be noted as: interviews. Additionally, wherever needed, internet resources from the respective CDI home pages were consulted.

Focus groups

Each FG was organized by APs in cooperation with CDIs and included three to six CDI members. In total, five FG sessions took place, as the Spanish CDIs were having the session together. The AP, namely the Institute of Agrifood Research and Technology (IRTA) organised the session with both Spanish CDI organisations at the same time due to their shared case

of work in the FOSTER project. The joint process for both CDIs was encouraged in order to build a mutual understanding of their common needs and differences. See Table 1 for an overview.

A FG question guide was developed, in order to ensure that all FG sessions were carried out in a comparable manner and covered the same key guiding questions, and also to ensure that all data required for the different WPs and activities within FOSTER are collected during the FG discussions. The guide was developed in five iterative steps. First step: the preliminary question guide was developed by WP3 task leaders based on the previous conversations with other WP leaders. Second step: sharing the question guide with the Steering Group. The third step involved the integration of the comments received in the pre-final question guide. The final fourth and fifth steps involved additional consultation with the Steering Group and integration of the final comments prior to sending the questions to the APs. The final question guide is in Appendix 3. Considering that FG sessions were a new form of interaction for some of the APs, WP3 members developed a short training about the basic principles involved in moderating an inclusive FG session. The slides of the FG training (author: Anna Struth) are available in the Appendix 4.

Table 1: The focus group session overview.

Day	AP	CDI (number of participants)	Country
25.04.2023	IRTA	Fab Lab IAAC (1) + Living Lab IrsiCaixa (3)	Spain
17.05.2023	KIS	PLP (3)	Hungary
22.05.2023	UHOH	ERS (3)	Germany
12.06.2023.	BIOS	DELTA (1) and stakeholders (3)	Serbia
13.06.2023	WUR	TcV (2) and stakeholder (1)	The Netherlands

All of the sessions were led by AP and with the presence of the CDI members. In order to bring diverse insights from the respective CDI partners, it was encouraged that there are at least two CDI members present during the FG sessions. In case of the Netherlands and Serbia, additional stakeholders involved in the CDIs work joined these sessions.

The FG sessions lasted approx. two hours each and were audio-recorded. The APs were asked to write a brief summary after the session concluded, and to subsequently upload the translated (from the local language into English) and anonymized transcripts. The FOSTER project data management plan was taken into consideration during the establishment of the FG sessions.

Consolidation of the baseline assessment for each CDI

For each CDI an assessment was created out of the data collected from the above-mentioned sources. To ensure that the CDIs have power over their own data, a first draft was sent to the CDIs for their feedback and input. This gave the CDIs a chance to add any missing items, if necessary correct information that might have been understood incorrectly during

the data collection process, and check whether all information provided can be made publicly available. In cases of correction provided by the CDIs, the reference for personal correspondence is added. Once this first round of feedback was incorporated, the CDIs also received an opportunity to review the full assessment report before submission.

Chapter 2

Overview of the change-driven initiatives

Chapter 2 – Overview of the change-driven initiatives

In this section we will provide summaries about each CDI – these summaries include: (1) information about the general background of each CDI (e.g., their history, type of organisation, size, funding sources), (2) CDI ambitions, activities, and theories of change, (3) CDI target stakeholder groups and networks, as well as (4) how CDIs interact with the K&I system.

2.1. DELTA Foundation and other collaborators – “Digital Village”

In the following summary, the attention will be brought towards “Digital Village,” which is a joint initiative of the CDI, namely Delta Foundation (abbreviation: DELTA), the AP namely BioSense Institute (BioSense), and a third organisation namely Mokrin House. “Digital Village” (in Serbian: “Digitalno Selo”) is an initiative that takes place in Mokrin village and was founded in 2021 by three stakeholders: DELTA, Mokrin House, and BioSense (which takes the role of the AP in the Serbian FOSTER case) (DELTA, survey; Digitalno selo, n.d.). Each of the three founding organisations brings their own background into the initiative and is still involved in the implementation. DELTA (in Serbian: Delta Fondacija) is a corporate philanthropic foundation situated in Belgrade, Serbia and is taking the role of the CDI. DELTA has experience in other rural community development projects, notably the “Our Village” (in Serbian: Naše Selo) initiative, which (like “Digital Village”) has worked to improve and modernize rural agricultural life in Serbia (Delta Holding, n.d.). It was founded in 2007 by Delta Holding (which also includes Delta Agrar, one of the largest agribusinesses in Serbia) as the Delta Humanitarian Fund (Delta Holding, n.d.). DELTA has a diverse portfolio of humanitarian and charitable projects, including building sports facilities for people with disabilities, supporting socially disadvantaged families, providing scholarships, and donating musical instruments and public art (Delta Foundation, n.d.). BioSense (in Serbian: BioSens Institut) is a research and development institute at the University of Novi Sad. They focus on developing “biosystem information technologies” for the digital transformation of the agricultural sector (BioSense, n.d.). Mokrin House is a self-described “avant-garde project”, a modern coworking and co-living space located in the village of Mokrin (Mokrin House, n.d.). Mokrin is the name of the village participating in the “Digital Village” initiative, and Mokrin House serves as the coordination hub between the village (i.e., the farmers and citizens of Mokrin) and the initiative, where meetings and training events are held (Digitalno selo, n.d.).

Altogether, “Digital Village” has five part-time employees, with three from DELTA and two from BioSense Institute (DELTA, survey). The initiative of “Digital Village” was originally planned as a three-year project, however it is expected to continue as long as there are needs for further village digitalisation, and until all project plans and activities are carried out (ibid.). Most of the activities around the “Digital Village” started together with the start of the FOSTER project.

CDI ambitions, activities, and theory of change

The stated mission of DELTA is “to meet the long-term social, educational, cultural, and healthcare needs of the community” (Delta Foundation, n.d.a). Table 2 provides an overview of examples of their agriculturally orientated

activities. Due to the shared initiative, it is worth noting the mission of BioSense (AP), which is “to provide the agricultural sector with superior digital solutions for achieving higher yields with less investment” (BioSense, n.d.a).

Table 2: Illustration of other activities coordinated by DELTA within the food domain, beyond the “Digital Village” (for more information about the latter, see Table 3).

Activity	Target group	Modes of action	Source of more information
“Plantation for Future”	Socially vulnerable low-income people, rural women, organisations supporting people with disabilities	Financial grants, professional assistance in modern production methodologies for fruit and vegetable cultivation and pig breeding	https://www.deltafondacija.rs/press-room/news/Results-of-the-project-Plantation-for-future.960.html
“Our Village” (Naše selo)	Rural communities (the villages of Dubočane, Mala Jasikova, Bačko Novo Selo)	Improving agricultural production (planning, education) and supporting cultural activities (building restoration, events)	https://naseselo.deltafondacija.rs/o-projektu/

The formal objective of the “Digital Village” initiative is to enable Mokrin to be the first village in Serbia to undergo the digital agriculture transformation process (DELTA, survey). The ambition of the “Digital Village” is to improve the livelihoods of farmers, first in Mokrin as the pilot area, then rolling out the initiative in other villages of Serbia, using Mokrin as a real-life proof of concept (ibid.). Table 3 lists the main activities that are part of the “Digital Village” initiative.

The big picture idea behind the “Digital Village” initiative is to counteract the ongoing rural flight (the depopulation of the countryside, particularly of young people who lack prospects for a desirable future) (DELTA, interview, Digitalno selo, n.d.). Their theory of change is that in order to prevent rural flight, rural livelihoods and quality of life need to be improved (ibid.). The method of action is to improve agricultural working conditions and increase yields (and thereby farm incomes) through the extension and deployment of appropriate technology, in particular the installation of wireless digital infrastructure (ibid.). Technology is seen as a driver towards the sustainability transition in the agricultural sector (ibid.).

Table 3: Illustration of activities included in the scope of the “Digital Village” initiative.

Activity	Target group	Modes of action	Source of more information
Development of digital platforms, including AgroSens (BioSense)	Mokrin farmers, Serbian farmers	Networking, connecting producers with customers and finance, and virtual cooperatives	https://digitalnoselo.rs/o-projektu/ https://www.agrosens.rs
Theoretical and practical training (Delta/BioSense)	Mokrin farmers	Teach farmers how to use digital tools and make data-informed decisions	https://digitalnoselo.rs/o-projektu/

Creation of individual development plans (Delta)	Mokrin farmers	Modernize production, optimize production, and business results	https://digitalnoselo.rs/o-projektu/
Installation of modern wireless digital infrastructure (BioSense)	Mokrin farmers	Enables use of modern agricultural technology, conserves water, and reduces input use	https://digitalnoselo.rs/o-projektu/
Extension of financial services, financial education (OTP Bank)	Mokrin farmers	Access to investment, loans for working capital, and financial advice	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/mokrin-house_projektu-digitalno-selo-koji-smo-pokrenuli-activity-7086646532623466496-OMd5

CDI target stakeholder group and networks

DELTA has a long-standing focus in rural development. Through their previous projects and their existing connections to Delta Agrar, they have a network of agricultural experts. They are also connected to financial institutions such as OTP Bank and Erste Bank, which is one of their partners for interest-free loans that serve rural development (VU interview). Through the BioSense Institute, there is close contact with researchers and the University of Novi Sad (BioSense, n.d.). Furthermore, Mokrin House provide both a physical place in Mokrin village and also community relationships and are an essential link to local farmers (DELTA, interview).

The proximal target group of the initiative are the farmers in and around Mokrin village. Over the long term, the “Digital Village” initiative would like to assist in the modernization of agricultural communities throughout Serbia. “Digital Village” stakeholders include local farmers, citizens of the village of Mokrin, researchers, agronomists, and financial institutions (DELTA, survey). It is important to acknowledge that all three organisations, namely, Delta Foundation, BioSense, and Mokrin House, which constitute the Digital Village initiative, all bring their own networks to the initiative.

CDI in the K&I system

As noted in the questionnaire and interview transcripts, the “Digital Village” initiative is not explicitly involved in any political processes. DELTA’s role in “Digital Village” is generally that of knowledge transfer - they get expert knowledge from their own employees, BioSense, governmental advisory services, and local agricultural experts, and this largely covers the task of advisory services (DELTA, interview). As part of the digitalisation of the village, farmers can get training on new digital tools (Digitalno selo, n.d.a). After the successful implementation of a “Digital Village,” Mokrin would serve as a real-life proof of viability and help to spread this approach (DELTA, survey).

2.2. Food Policy Council City Region Stuttgart

Food Policy Council City Region Stuttgart (in German: Ernährungsrat StadtRegion Stuttgart; abbreviation: ERS) is a registered voluntary association (e.V., eingetragener Verein) that was officially founded in 2021 (Ernährungsrat

StadtRegion Stuttgart e.V., n.d.) and is physically based in the city of Stuttgart (Germany). As indicated in the survey, the ERS mission is to transform the food system in the city and region of Stuttgart towards the production and consumption of ecologic, sustainable, and climate-friendly food (ERS, survey).

ERS has an elected board of three directors, who work on a voluntary basis. Two of them together are allowed to legally represent the association (ERS, survey). Since 2022, the association is financially supported by the city government of Stuttgart and has two part-time employees (ERS, focus group). According to the ERS team, in 2021 there were already 13 members, who represent different sectors of the food system like agriculture, research, and food processing for instance. The members are seen as actors for change as far as possible, and ERS aims to take their needs into consideration (ERS, survey). Membership fees vary from 12 to over 100 euros per year and make up part (0.5%) of the ERS budget (data from 2022, ERS, survey). ERS is currently collaborating in two European projects, namely, FOSTER and HuMUS (see Table 5) in which the team collaborates with the University of Hohenheim (Germany) (UHOH) (ERS, focus group).

CDI ambitions, activities, and theory of change

The main aspects that are addressed in the food system by ERS are: general food awareness, what is healthy, sustainable, and organic (ERS, survey). Further, an ERS member during the FGs session notes that part of the CDI's role is to be in touch for example with the farmers and food producers to integrate their perspective into the food strategy for Stuttgart, as well as to create a connection between those producing food, policy makers, and citizens.

As part of their main activities, ERS is developing a food strategy for the region of Stuttgart (ERS, focus group). As specified during the FG, ERS aims to be an open platform for actors from civil society like NGOs, business, and institutions who are committed to a sustainable and just food system. These actors are included in six working groups for developing the food strategy of the region (ERS, focus group). Within the food strategy there are six different areas: production and marketing; land and soil; food hub and logistics; climate protection; communication; and out-of-home catering (ibid). ERS created six corresponding working groups which develop the goals and steps in each area. ERS elaborate the goal for these working groups as follows: "In the first meetings, we want to formulate the goals of a transformation, discuss issues, outline solutions and needs, and agree on next steps. From this, a joint nutrition strategy for the Stuttgart Region is to be developed over the next few years." The food strategy for Stuttgart region will be a guidance to transform the food system on several layers (ERS, focus group). Diverse actors are invited to participate in the process, from producers, processors, and gastronomists, to city officials and politicians, as well as private initiatives and interested citizens (ibid.). Through including diverse actors into the process, ERS aims to involve the whole city society. They want to create results that are adoptable and supported by different actors (ERS, focus group).

As noted during the FG, ERS wants to become the umbrella organisation for all food-related organisations, initiatives, businesses, and institutions which are active in the food system of Stuttgart. The ERS sees themselves as a facilitator for change, who creates connections between knowledge, innovation, and people (ibid.). As emphasized during the ERS survey, "people should gain knowledge to educate/activate/wake up citizens to act as catalysts for innovation."

In the kick-off meeting, Ulrich Ostarhild (at that time a board member of ERS), elaborated: "Citizens have lost contact with their food source and don't relate to the "soil to table." Local and seasonal foods need to increase importance to

rebuild this connection. The aim is to enable consumers to decide on food that is good for themselves and the environment.” (Ulrich Ostarhild, kick-off notes). For this, the consumer should get insights behind the scenes of food production. See Table 4 for more activities.

Table 4: Illustration of activities coordinated by ERS within the food domain.

Activity	Target group	Modes of action	Source of more information
Food strategy	All actors of the food system	Six groups working in different topics, strategy for the whole city	https://www.ernaehrungsrat-stuttgart.de/arbeitsgruppen
Food Hub feasibility study	Decision makers, producers, processors	A hub for regionally/locally produced food	https://www.ernaehrungsrat-stuttgart.de/projekt/machbarkeitsstudie-food-hub
Campaign “My little bit more Stuttgart“	Citizens	Network activities, events, and educational offers	https://www.ernaehrungsrat-stuttgart.de/projekt/kampagne-mein-bisschen-mehr-stuttgart
Mapping food system	Citizens	A research project for students of the Hohenheim M.Sc. program “Organic Agriculture & Food Systems“	https://www.ernaehrungsrat-stuttgart.de/projekt/mapping-ernaehrungssystem
EU project HuMUS	Citizens, local decision makers	EU Horizon project to increase awareness of importance of soil health in local communities	https://www.ernaehrungsrat-stuttgart.de/projekt/eu-projekte

CDI target stakeholder group and networks

ERS target group are actors from civil society, business and institutions who are committed to a sustainable and just food system. For future activities the aim for ERS is to do more activities with youth, women, and underrepresented groups (ERS, survey).

On a local level, one target group are citizens who should be empowered to make informed food decisions (ERS, focus group). Another target group are local producers, processors, and gastronomy, who will be supported through the development of stronger local supply chains. Another important target group are local decision makers, who are enabled to make better policy decisions through the food strategy.

On a regional level, ERS closely collaborate with the city of Stuttgart, especially the department of climate protection (in German: Stabsstelle Klimaschutz) (ERS, focus group), who is also administrating part of the funding (ERS personal correspondence). ERS further collaborate with the representatives who organise canteen catering in public kindergartens and schools (ERS, focus group). These city representatives named above are also involved in developing the food strategy for Stuttgart (ERS, focus group). Further, ERS collaborate with the manager of the organic model region (Biomusterregion) Stuttgart-Ludwigsburg, a state-funded position which promotes organic and local agriculture (ERS, focus group). UHOH is their main partner for research both in the EU Horizon projects as well as smaller projects (ibid.). There are also several

partners in urban gardening, such as Chloroplast e.V. and Stadtacker, as well as connections to agricultural producers (ERS, interview).

There are many organisations within the area of Stuttgart which are active in the same field and to whom ERS would want to involve in their work. As emphasized by ERS member during the interview: “We are just getting started with the networking, so that the current state is rather dynamic and evolving, we are a ‘new player in the field’” (ERS member, interview).

On a larger scale, ERS is both part of a network with other food policy councils in the state of Baden-Württemberg as well as in the German-wide network for food policy councils (ERS, survey). ERS also have connections to the Baden Württemberg State Ministry of Agriculture and the German Ministry of Agriculture. Additionally, they network with parliamentary decision makers in the Landtag von Baden-Württemberg (Parliament of Baden-Württemberg) (ibid). ERS also holds a cooperation with Slow Food e.V. for specific events (ERS, interview).

ERS members have diverse backgrounds in the food system, e.g., agricultural production, organic agriculture certification, fair trade, research, and politics, as well as gastronomy. This means that due to their members, the ERS have many different connections within the food system (ERS, focus group).

CDI in the K&I system

ERS is more focused on social innovation and networking as well as trying to promote local food knowledge and value chains than on technical innovations (Table 3). Additionally, ERS tries to incubate new ideas and help them to emerge (ERS, focus group). They recently started a regular meeting which is open to anyone interested in the food policy council. In these meetings they visit different local production, processing, and consumption places that are in line with their food vision (personal correspondence). Additionally, ERS together with UHOH is creating a map of the food network in the city of Stuttgart (ERS, focus group). This map will be publicly available and mark the physical locations as well as provide background information on them (ibid.). The ERS wants to increase knowledge about and visibility for these places through the meetings and maps (ibid.).

ERS is part of two EU projects that both have a strong focus on creating knowledge for local initiatives and communities that is applicable and directly incorporate into activities with citizens (ERS, focus group). Therefore, they are part of the knowledge creation while also having the role to spread the created knowledge.

2.3. Fab Lab Barcelona

Fab Lab Barcelona holds a physical space in Poblenou, Barcelona (Spain) at the Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia (IAAC), where most of their activities with the communities take place (Fab Lab, survey). Fab Lab Barcelona was the first Fab Lab founded in the European Union in 2007 and is a benchmark in the powerful network and open-source movement of over 1800 Fab Labs in more than 100 countries (ibid.). As an association, the Fab Lab Barcelona does research and offers educational programs, e.g., Master in Design for Emergent Futures, as well as the Fab Academy and Fabricademy which are postgraduate programs which last several months in collaboration with the Fab Foundation

(<https://fabfoundation.org/>) and the MIT's Center for Bits and Atoms (<https://cba.mit.edu/>). Part of the funding comes from offering educational programs, as well as through EU research projects (Horizon, Creative Europe, and Erasmus+), while another part is through third-party funding, providing products and services. The institution supports contemporary educational and research programs related to the multiple scales of the human habitat (Fab Lab personal correspondence).

CDI ambitions, activities, and theory of change

The Fab Lab Barcelona understands themselves as an innovation centre who is rethinking the way we live, work, and play in cities (Fab Lab, survey). In their own words, the Fab Lab Barcelona have the mission of approximating knowledge and technologies to the people, to the citizens, so that they can empower themselves and create their own projects, their own ideas, bring them down from a conceptual way to a tangible and real way" (Fab Lab, focus group). As noted by the Fab Lab Barcelona members: "our goal is to be that partner or that place where you can find everything you need to create your idea from scratch" (Fab Lab, *ibid.*). As indicated by the Fab Lab Barcelona team members, projects led by the Fab Lab Barcelona potentially use open technologies or open innovation (Fab Lab personal correspondence). That means that they are more likely accessible within everyone's reach and available to citizens (Fab Lab, focus group). Within the projects, Fab Lab Barcelona co-creates with the citizens, Communities of Practice, students and multiple stakeholders from the scoping phase (e.g., Making Sense toolkit and SISCODE toolbox). Another key element is that everything they create from this co-creation process is encouraged to be open source (Fab Lab, focus group).

During the interviews, a Fab Lab Barcelona member emphasized that a stronger focus on food and food technologies emerged during the COVID-19 pandemic. In the kick-off event, the Fab Lab Barcelona members brought their approach towards FoodSHIFT2030 with the ambition of more productive cities (Fab Lab, kick-off notes). Fab Lab Barcelona wants to spark new narratives about food and system change (Fab Lab, kick-off notes). These include aquaponics, vertical farms, and the cultivation of food in private houses using designed kits (Fab Lab, interview), overall, its Food Tech 3.0 (<https://fablabbcn.org/blog/lab-life/this-was-food-tech-3-0-a-recap-of-the-acceleration-program>) based on the following pillars, built from the FoodSHIFT 2030 approach and Fab Lab Barcelona vision to food: tech that is community-based, citizen-powered and encourages food citizenship; addresses holistic sustainability; incorporates open design practices; operates in an ecosystem of actors; and prioritises equity and accessibility. See the following Table 5 for more detailed EU Projects activities.

Table 5: Illustration of activities coordinated by Fab Lab Barcelona within the food domain.

Initiatives name	Target group	Modes of action	Source of more information
FOODSHIFT2030 project, Barcelona Food Tech 3.0 Lab	Citizens	Development and piloting of open-source technology for production, elaboration, consumption, and re-/upcycling of food in cities for accelerating local food tech initiatives; Food Tech 3.0 FoodSHIFT2030 Accelerator Lab	https://foodshift2030.eu/

Remix The School	People in the educational ecosystem	Creation of new learning dimensions and projects with food waste to enhance learning outcomes	https://fablabbcn.org/projects/remix-the-school
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CDI target stakeholder group and networks

Much of their work is with students within the academic framework, and also citizens and communities of practice are engaged in the research projects and in the education projects of the students (Fab Lab, interview). The actions and solutions are co-created with involved students, neighbourhood associations, civil associations, and the private sector (Fab Lab, focus group). Fab Lab Barcelona team wants to support people in creating their own solutions (Fab Lab, focus group). Fab Lab Barcelona is part of the worldwide network of Fab Labs, with a network of over 1800 partners around the world (Fab Lab, *ibid.*). In their work, the Fab Lab team collaborates with academia and the public sector, as well as technicians and the private sector (Fab Lab, *ibid.*). Especially in the San Martí area (Poblenou neighbourhood), the Fab Lab Barcelona team also work a lot with the private sector and with the neighbourhood associations and the civil associations (Fab Lab, *ibid.*). It was also noted during the FG session that the Fab Lab Barcelona collaborates with different universities, depending on the focus of the project (Fab Lab, focus group).

CDI in the K&I system

Fab Lab Barcelona produces research and innovation based around the digital fabrication laboratory, which is the heart of the organisation (Fab Lab, survey). They focus on innovation around the value chain (Fab Lab, interview). The Fab Lab Barcelona is focused on projects that link research, design, and technology (Table 5): “We are a research and education centre rethinking the way we live, work and play!” (Fab Lab Barcelona, n.d.). A large share of their work is offering educational programs where students engage with the challenges and are empowered to start changes locally. As specified in the survey: “Our method is to propose small-scale interventions to approach large-scale challenges, in order to dissolve wicked problems, instead of solving them with single moonshot solutions” (Fab Lab, survey). Fab Lab Barcelona uses rapid prototyping and ideas testing as an important element in their educational approach, and students learn new skills on the go (Fab Lab, interview). It is important to acknowledge that their solutions are open source based, which makes them accessible for citizens (Fab Lab, interview). Further, they also exchange ideas and knowledge with their international network (Fab Lab, interview). Also, for their research projects they try to engage directly with communities of practice and share their research results with them (*ibid.*). Fab Lab Barcelona is also involved in knowledge production through several research projects and cooperate with other research institutions (*ibid.*). Some of their projects are specifically focused on co-creation and co-design, as well as intentionally involving diverse actors and perspectives (*ibid.*).

2.4. Living Lab IrsiCaixa

The Living Lab for Health at IrsiCaixa (in Spanish: Living Lab de Salud de IrsiCaixa, abbreviation: Living Lab) is a department embedded in a research centre, namely, IrsiCaixa and based in Spain (Living Lab, survey). Ms. Rosina Malagrida founded

the Living Lab IrsiCaixa in 2016 after the team started working in operationalizing Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) within the European Commission (EC) funded project called RRI Tools. They have more than 10 years of experience in the field of RRI as part of other EC funded projects (ibid.). The Living Lab IrsiCaixa team notes their mission as following: “to facilitate innovation networks to contribute to the resolution of complex and persistent health challenges. These challenges are persistent because innovation is not achieving the desired impact due to the current fragmented model of the research and innovation system. The Living Lab IrsiCaixa designs and implements integrated interventions to address them through the multistakeholder innovation networks” (ibid.). Holding a physical office with four employees, the Living Lab IrsiCaixa also has more than 70 volunteers who form part of the networks they facilitate or assess (ibid.).

CDI ambitions, activities, and theory of change

When it comes to defining the food system, the Living Lab IrsiCaixa during the FG session noted the following: “it is a system in which different areas of knowledge converge and in which many actors participate. From those of us who are involved in the value chain to all those who are not in the value chain, but who in the end are indirectly related to food, such as the education sector, the health sector, the environmental sector, the environment as such” (Living Lab, focus group). During the interviews, Living Lab IrsiCaixa noted that according to them, food system transformation is a very ambitious challenge, with several sub-challenges. Therefore, they focus mostly on one of these sub-challenges, namely ‘healthy diets’ (Living Lab, interviews). They believe that in the current state, solutions for healthy diets are not accessible to the vulnerable areas of Barcelona (ibid.). Although there are NGOs or other initiatives who work on those issues, they do not reach the vulnerable areas (ibid.). Living Lab IrsiCaixa sees a need for low-cost interventions to promote healthy diets for those areas (ibid.). They take on the function of managing, making approaches more systemic and effective, through systemic intervention (developed in Fit4Food: decentralized and coordinated) (ibid.). See Table 6 for more details on the activities.

Table 6: Illustration of activities coordinated by the Living Lab IrsiCaixa within the food domain.

Activity	Target group	Modes of action	Source of more information
Complex intervention to promote healthy and sustainable food habits- Alison innovation network – EU funded project Fit4Food2030	Barcelona neighbourhood of La Verneda i La Pau	Design and implementation of complex intervention through system innovation and TD approaches within a network created for this purpose	https://www.irsicaixa.es/en/living-lab-health/projects/alison
Complex Intervention to promote healthy and sustainable food habits- EU funded project FoodClic	Two vulnerable neighbourhoods in the Barcelona City Region (Àrea Metropolitana de Barcelona)	System innovation and transdisciplinary (TD) approaches to design and implement integrated interventions in neighbourhoods and increase impact of existing ones by expanding the Alison Network	https://foodclic.eu/

Complex Intervention for mental health promotion – EU funded project CONNECT and Sentinel School Network	Schools, families, local government	Design and implementation of a complex intervention with system innovation and TD approaches with different iterations that facilitate students to personalize their solutions with a systems approach	https://www.irsicaixa.es/en/living-lab-health/projects/sentinel-schools-network
Complex intervention for Long Covid and other complex health challenges- Barcelona CaixaResearch Living Lab	Researchers at IrsiCaixa, in collaboration with key stakeholders (i.e., healthcare providers, patients, patient associations, etc.)	Promotion of collective impact through integrated interventions that combine drug and non-drug treatments and promote knowledge integration within and among them	https://www.irsicaixa.es/en/living-lab-health/projects/long-covid

CDI target stakeholder group and networks

The Living Lab IrsiCaixa team is involved in numerous networks such as the Alison innovation network, Sentinel School Network Study Group as well as Long Covid Network (Living Lab, survey). As part of each network, the Living Lab is involved in several tasks (ibid.). Additionally, the Living Lab IrsiCaixa is a member of the Living Knowledge Network, the System Innovation Platform, and, as part of IrsiCaixa, they are members of a Catalan network of research centres called CERCA (ibid.).

Through these numerous networks, the Living Lab IrsiCaixa is engaged with different stakeholders. As for example, as part of the Alison innovation network, the Living Lab notes the following stakeholder groups: universities, research centres, primary care centres, public health agencies, hospitals, cultural centres, primary and secondary schools, city and regional councils, social and community services, stores, and restaurants (Living Lab, survey). When it comes to the Sentinel School Network Study Group, the following stakeholders are named: school directors, teachers, students and their families, healthcare providers, civil society organisations and patient associations (ibid.). In the Long Covid Network, stakeholders include healthcare providers and managers from primary care and hospitals, a patient association, and researchers from IrsiCaixa (ibid.). However, the Lab members add that: “(...) at this moment, we are working with organisations and at the administration level.” (Living Lab, interviews). During personal correspondence, the Living Lab team adds, that in each Network different citizens groups are also involved e.g., in the Alison network – lay citizens, in the Long Covid network – patients and in the Sentinel School Network we have families.

Meanwhile, the Living Lab IrsiCaixa emphasizes: “We [the Living Lab] get involved in different projects that want to address health promotion challenges. And then, based on different frameworks such as system innovation, through different methodologies, we work with the stakeholders involved to be able to design integrated solutions that address the complexity of these challenges” (Living Lab, ibid.). The Living Lab IrsiCaixa team also reflected, that what they do is facilitate self-agency, which was defined by their members as, “when people commit to working with us on this challenge, they make it their own, so they believe in it” (ibid.).

CDI in the K&I system

Living Lab members during the interview specify as follows: “what we do from the Living Lab is to facilitate networks for collective impact. Of course, with multi stakeholders. And we call them innovation networks, because they are networks where what we want to achieve is to see the transformation of a system. And for that we need innovation. And what we bring in with our first strategic phase, always, we design an integrated strategy. And always for complex health challenges” (Living Lab, interview). Living Lab also provides explanation on a methodology as part of innovation programmes that they have developed which consists of four phases (Figure 1). “The phase one is a participatory research project for strategic design with systems innovation approaches. So, we design the integrated intervention here. Once we know what we want to do, and how we are going to organize together, we move to the second phase, which is co-creation. And in the second phase is when we design the prototypes of the solutions. In phase three, we first pilot and then we scale up. And in phase four, reflexive monitoring is in action” (Living Lab, interview). On the question where does the knowledge come from, the Living Lab team provides an example of a project they were part of regarding the development of a tool which measures the healthy and sustainable offers of shops. During this project, while partnering with research organisations as well as international organisations e.g., with the Open University of Catalonia, who, in turn, is collaborating with Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO) the Living Lab brought the aspect in of making the research (descriptive in type) more transformative. In this particular project “our role [Living Lab] there is that one [to make sure that the descriptive tool can be useful as a transformative change tool], the knowledge comes from them [the university]. But we join in with our knowledge on transformative change with our methodologies (with the four phases) [that we explained to you] that we combine with their tool, to invite stakeholders in these shops to start with this system thinking to explore the current situation, a future vision, therefore reflecting on the present and the future. Creating what we call a creative tension and then inviting them to think about solutions with transformative knowledge, and so on. In this manner, we make sure that this descriptive research that they were already doing is no longer only descriptive, but it’s used as a learning process for shops to transform” (Living Lab, interview).

As emphasized by the Living Lab IrsiCaixa team, de-centralized actions are one of their working approaches (Living Lab, interview). They mention, that: “in fact in our case, every time we start facilitating a new innovation ecosystem, we do redefine the strategy and therefore we implement phase 1 to develop local knowledge again because we understand that there's complexity behind it, so it requires adjusting that to that reality” (Living Lab, focus group).

Figure 1: Phases to be implemented iteratively for transition innovation. Source: Living Lab IrsiCaixa.

2.5. Pannon Helyi Termék Nonprofit Ltd.

Pannonian Local Products Nonprofit Ltd. (in Hungarian: Pannon Helyi Termék Nonprofit Kft; abbreviation: PLP) is a non-profit organisation situated in the western part of Hungary, in Vas County near the Austrian border (PLP, interview). The English name of the organisation is translated as Pannonian Local Products, which illustrates the main focus of the organisation. The history of the organisation dates back to 2005, when the PLP Cluster was initiated by 13 organisations, including local government, folk-art organisations, and agritourism alliances (PLP, interview). The collaboration as part of the cluster was one of the first initiatives across Hungary to help small-scale farmers (ibid.). In 2007, the cluster was turned into a management organisation, i.e., a non-profit Ltd, and this has remained its legal form until now (ibid.). Holding a physical office, the organisation operates with 10 employees, has 16 consortium members (in the framework of an EU call for proposals aimed at the development of short food supply chains), and approx. 70-80 informal members in the network (PLP, survey). One of the services offered for their formal and informal members is the right to use the “Pannon Local Products” trademark and logo (with the requirement to meet the qualification criteria (ibid.)), (see “Pannon Local Products” trademark and logo in Pannon Helyi Termék, 2023). There are no membership fees (PLP, survey).

CDI ambitions, activities, and theory of change

As noted by the PLP members, “The founders would like to help local handicraft products, agricultural and food products to find their market by creating a unified image and by finding individual sales solutions. Another important objective is to higher [increase] the employment and to give some income generate solutions in these rural areas” (PLP member, interview question). The organisation notes that the future plans for them: “include strong awareness-rising activities in the mindset of the customers, trainings for the producers, [and] technological, product, and packaging development” (ibid.). In personal correspondence, the PLP team stated the following aim: “(...) to boost the local economy, help local livelihoods by keeping money local, and strengthen local food production and consumption”. The PLP team added, “We have wide range of activities supporting local producers, farmers, and handicraftsman in our territory. Most important is boosting collaboration and building networks between stakeholders of [the] local food system to increase market share of small-scale farmers” (PLP, survey). Up-to-date information about producers, their products, and the organisation's services are available via the PLP Web shop (https://www.pannonhelyitermek.hu/shop_contact.php). During the FG session, PLP noted that their goal is for “those who deal with these methods [old crafts and food production methods] how they can receive a financial and professional support impulse so that they do not stop this otherwise valuable activity. So, to save!”.

To achieve their mission, “the level of self-sufficiency of the region will be increasingly higher. The quantity of local producers and products meet the demands” (PLP member, interview). PLP has undertaken several activities, including a market analysis based on the views of 100 producers within the region of Western Transdanubia; building networks between stakeholders of the local food system to increase the market share of small-scale farmers; and developing numerous local initiatives, such as a local farmers' market, a box scheme, a restaurant focused on local cuisine and local products, thematic days at the farmers' markets, food tastings, gastronomy shows, visits to the farms, etc., see Table 7.

Table 7: Illustration of activities coordinated by the PLP within the food domain.

Initiatives name	Target group	Modes of action	Source of more information
Weekly local farmers markets at Szombathely and Vasvár	500 customers a week, mainly: pensioners, families with children	Market activities with local products (every Thursday at Szombathely and every Wednesday at Vasvár since 2014)	https://www.facebook.com/pannon.helyitermek
Box scheme (Green Basket)	More than 100 consumers and 20-30 farmers	Consumers can pick up their boxes of local products every Thursday of the week after placing an order online	https://vasizoldkosar.hu/
Restaurant at Szombathely	Approx. 2000-3000 consumers, mainly from Szombathely's younger communities	Local product tastings and wine evenings	https://www.facebook.com/kilences.cafe
Workshops, visits to the farms	Approx. 500 participants per year	Experiential workshops e.g., learning traditional craft making, applying traditional recipes	https://www.facebook.com/vasvar.nepfoiskola https://nepfovasvar.hu/
“Give Place to Locals” campaign	Local consumers and producers	Network to promote local products and handicrafts, increase points of sale	http://www.pannonproduct.hu/adj-helyet-a-helyinek

Nowadays, the organisations and their professional partnership are working on refreshing their brand (PLP, personal correspondence). The aim is to provide consumers with quality products, knowledge, and experiences, building on the already well-established local product distribution channels and places (ibid.). In addition, their main objective is to bring together and support the networking efforts of those who want to do something for the Hungarian farming community, for healthy local food available to all, for quality agri-tourism and catering (ibid.). The main logo includes 3 aspects (see Figure 2). Each logo marks a place where customers can find local foods, handicraft products, and healthy locally-sourced delicacies: <https://www.facebook.com/helybenvagyunk> (ibid.).

Figure 2: “We are local” trademark and logo.

CDI target stakeholder group and networks

When it comes to listing involved stakeholders in the initiative, PLP members noted the following: local farmers, local government, concerned citizens, civic organisations, agritourism associations, and national parks. Additionally, PLP has been part of West-Pannon Team network for 10 years (<https://www.westpannon.hu/en>). Since 2011, the West-Pannon Team works on local to trans-national projects in sustainable regional development across Western Transdanubia (West-Pannon Nonprofit Ltd., n.d.). According to the PLP team, “the network is engaged in sustainable regional development based upon co-operation, expertise and the values of nature and culture” (PLP member, survey).

CDI in the K&I system

PLP now is a key player among organisations committed to local food system development in Hungary. However, during the kick-off event of the project meeting, PLP noted that, “we need more access to local farmers: 'how can we have local farmers work more together?' (...), we also desire more knowledge about technologies that farmers can use in their day-to-day activities”. With regards to knowledge exchange, PLP keeps up to date on legislative changes, current trends, and good practices from foreign countries (PLP, focus group). During the FG session, PLP added that “(...) it is from network cooperation that we also learn from each other.” PLP members expressed the question on knowledge production for involved stakeholders. The following summarises the essence: “It is knowledge itself to make it available: such as, e.g., innovations to invent something completely new, such as product development; or let's adopt proven things, good examples; and let's take the producers on study trips” (PLP member, focus group). Repeatedly PLP members stressed the importance of “connecting processes, people and ideas” (ibid.) when it comes to collaboration and knowledge transfer question. “We do a lot in the field of knowledge transfer, but it can still be improved and organized into a system” (ibid.).

2.6. Transitiecoalitie Voedsel

Food Transition Coalition (in Dutch: Transitiecoalitie Voedsel; abbreviated: TcV) is a foundation that was started in 2017 by three people who met at a Sustainability Forum (TcV, survey). It has grown to be a coalition of around 200 people and organisations, including around 125 paying members in the inner circle, with a second circle called “Friends of TcV,” which are companies and organisations who are part of TcV’s network and who also provide financial support (ibid.). TcV has an office in Utrecht, the Netherlands as part of an office-sharing arrangement, and a dozen people work (mostly part-time, freelance, remotely) for the foundation (ibid.). The governance structure of TcV is one formal director, supported by a three-person management team, who are supervised by the Supervisory and Inspiration Board (ibid.).

CDI ambitions, activities, and theory of change

TcV describes themselves as “a collective of transition thinkers and doers who want to give direction to the agrifood transition” (TcV, survey). Their stated motto is, “a healthy life on a healthy planet. For everyone” (ibid.). TcV see themselves as having two main roles: firstly, as challengers, as catalysts for change, by raising topics and initiating action; and secondly as connectors, bringing frontrunners and pioneers from different areas together (ibid.). TcV is currently

focused on three main themes: the protein transition, sustainable agriculture (including soil and human health), and rewards and pricing (ibid.). See Table 8 for more details on the activities.

Table 8: Illustration of activities coordinated by the TcV within the food domain.

Initiatives name	Target group	Modes of action	Source of more information
Plant The Future Dinner	Businesses, banks, supermarkets, farmers, science, NGOs, and politicians from different parties	Farm Kitchen during Dutch Food week, putting the protein on the table and the political agenda	https://plantthefuture.eu/
Spokespersons of the Future	General public, readers of https://maatschapwij.nu/ (a sustainability/social change website)	Series of stories from visionaries who can inspire farmers in making future-proof choices	https://transitiecoalitievoedsel.nl/woordvoerders-van-de-toekomst/

TcV's principles are articulated in their vision (2017), which contains 10 points (Transitiecoalitie Voedsel, n.d.). These include true cost pricing, regenerative agriculture, and transitioning towards plant-based proteins (their three main foci), as well as other points such as transparency, short supply chains, fairness and access, and human and planetary health (ibid.). Their general theory of change is illustrated in Figure 3, where individuals see the possibility of change, who then start to connect and organise until they reach a critical mass, and this leads to a policy shift and institutionalisation.

Figure 3: Transition Phases (Transitiecoalitie Voedsel, n.d.a).

Figure 3 is one half of the “X-curve” (Figure 4, below) that TcV use in tandem to visualize their theory of change, where the rising “S-curve” of adoption in Figure 4 is mirrored by a falling curve of decline and phase-out.

Figure 4: “X-curve” pattern of transformational change (based on Loorbach (2014), Transitiecoalitie Voedsel, n.d.a).

CDI target stakeholder group and networks

As is written in their aforementioned motto, TcV’s stated target group is “for everyone,” but not necessarily through direct interaction with citizens. Their focus is on creating system change at the national level (the Netherlands), particularly by influencing policy, it can be understood that their proximal target group/lever for change is policy makers, which include not only politicians but also industry (TcV, personal correspondence). Thus, due to political and market developments, TcV also focus on businesses (ibid.).

CDI in the K&I system

TcV’s role in the K&I systems is that of “superconnector”, connecting pioneering networks and actors, and using these connections to lobby for change. They work, either thematically or on an individual project basis, with like-minded parties (TcV, survey). These include farmer organisations (e.g., Herenboeren, Boerenraad, community supported agriculture organisations), other networks (e.g., Green Protein Alliance, MVO Nederland, RIDLV, TAPP Coalition), NGOs (e.g. Hart Stichting, Voeding Leeft, Natuur & Milieu), community initiatives (e.g., Rotterdam de boer op, Amsterdam Voedsel Verbindt), and experts or knowledge institutions (e.g. Wageningen University and Research, Louis Bolk Institute, Nyenrode University, HAS University, NWO (Dutch Research Council)) (TcV, survey). Within their coalition, TcV works with numerous organisations, including start-ups and “scale-ups” (TcV, personal correspondence). Some of their partners receive funding from local and regional governments in the Netherlands (TcV, focus group). TcV also uses their resources to research topics (e.g., the effects of soil health on human health and nutrition), and they hold webinars to disseminate their findings (TcV, interview).

Chapter 3

Synthesis

Chapter 3 – Synthesis

Across the FOSTER project, six CDIs are working on food systems from numerous angles. The CDIs are physically situated across five countries, see Figure 5. Fab Lab and PLP were both started in 2007, which means that they have established a history which enables them to look back on and gain perspective from their previous activities. Although TcV was founded in 2017 and Living Lab IrsiCaixa in 2016, the organisations already have experience with collaborating in international and national projects. Both ERS and “Digital Village” are newly established initiatives that are still running their first projects and building their network. In the case of “Digital Village,” although the initiative itself is new, the involved partners are well-established in their fields. Especially for ERS, it is one of their main priorities at the moment to establish themselves as an umbrella organisation between other existing organisations within the Stuttgart area.

Figure 5: The representation of the involved CDIs. Credit: FOSTER project.

3.1. CDI activities, ambitions, and K&I

The six CDIs in FOSTER are quite heterogenous in every way – not only geographically, but also in their structural organisation, their foci, and modes of action. See Table 9.

Table 9: Overview of the FOSTER project CDIs.

CDI name	Country	Target group	Modes of action
Delta Foundation –“Digital Village“	Serbia	Farmers in Mokrin	Extension, education, and technology support
Ernährungsrat StadtRegion Stuttgart e.V.	Germany	Food actors and civil society in Stuttgart	Networking, lobbying, education
Fab Lab Barcelona IAAC	Spain	Students, civil society	Education, research
Living Lab IrsiCaixa	Spain	Food actors in the Barcelona city region, health professionals and researchers	Networking, connecting different actors, implementation, education, research, integrating social, technological and policy innovation
Pannonian Local Products Nonprofit Ltd.	Hungary	Small scale farmers, food producers, consumers	Implementation, connecting different actors, networking
Transitiecoalitie Voedsel	The Netherlands	Policy makers	Lobbying, connecting different actors

Four initiatives have the status of a formal organisation, with TcV being a foundation, while ERS and PLP are non-profit organisations. Fab Lab as an association is part of the Institute for Advanced Architecture Living Lab, whereas Living Lab IrsiCaixa is a department in a research centre, namely, IrsiCaixa. As for the “Digital Village” – the initiative does not have a formal organisational status, but instead is a joint initiative by three organisations that also employ the workforce. All organisations have at least part-time employees that work for them. The respective CDIs vary in their sizes. For example, while ERS only has two part-time employees and two to three active volunteers, Fab Lab has several employees. Some of the employees in the “Digital Village” are employed through DELTA as well as by partner organisations, i.e., BioSense and Delta Holding. TcV and ERS have part-time staff who also work in other jobs within the food sector. Fab Lab and ERS generate most of their funding through projects, while TcV also gains a substantial share of their budget through their membership payments and charitable donations.

Each of the initiatives are embedded across different parts of the food system. As for example, the activities as part of “Digital Village” are largely linked to digital agriculture. PLP has the aim of preserving their local traditions and supporting local production and consumption. ERS, Living Lab IrsiCaixa, and FabLab hold similar ambitions of being a platform for stakeholders, where they can work on their own projects. The concept used by Living Lab IrsiCaixa regarding “self-agency” is also particularly visible across the initiatives of Fab Lab and PLP. Although TcV has three focal themes, i.e., the protein transition, agriculture (particularly soil and human health), and rewards and pricing, a similarity to the other CDIs is the approach of being the connector, i.e., bringing different stakeholders together.

To state the obvious, all six CDIs are actively involved in knowledge creation through their participation in the FOSTER project. This is obviously not the primary focus of any of the CDIs. Rather, it follows from their respective approaches to instigating change. Both Fab Lab as well as “Digital Village” are focused on technological solutions, but for different target groups. Fab Lab aims to empower urban citizens to become food producers or processors with accessible tech solutions, in line with open-source values. This means new solutions (which can be copied and adapted by others) are created and spread via the international Fab Lab network. On the other hand, “Digital Village” supports farmers in applying digital farming solutions and using them to increase their yields. The village of Mokrin is the starting point, and this approach shall then be used in other villages around Serbia. Living Lab IrsiCaixa is the only organisation with a strong focus on integrating knowledge around health and healthy diets to facilitate integrated strategies of technological, social and policy innovations. TcV is focused on finding solutions and applying them on a policy level, mainly on a national scale. Also, ERS is aiming to apply their solutions on a policy level, but much more focused on their regional level. Both ERS and PLP aim for social innovations that support the agricultural producers and processors they collaborate with, ERS being more focused on urban contexts, while PLP focusses more on a rural context. PLP also encourages maintaining the value of traditional products and handicrafts.

Some CDIs, like Living Lab IrsiCaixa and ERS, are more driven towards making knowledge about the food system accessible for the consumers to change their habits, while “Digital Village” is targeting agricultural producers. Both PLP and ERS try to find innovative approaches for improving local value chains and thereby supporting agricultural producers.

3.2. CDI target stakeholder group and networks

The scope of area in which the CDIs are active vary from urban to rural food systems. Fab Lab, ERS, and Living Lab IrsiCaixa address the food systems in and around cities. While TcV is more oriented towards networking at the national level, “Digital Village” and PLP are focused on improving farmers’ livelihoods in rural areas. They therefore have a strong network of local farms and local producers. Additionally, PLP supports their members in creating distribution and sales channels. Of all the initiatives, Fab Lab and the Living Lab IrsiCaixa have the most visible experiences in international cooperation. While Fab Lab has many local programs, they also see themselves as part of a global network of Fab Labs that have the same underlying values around open source and open access technologies. Since much of the work of TcV is on a national level, they also have strong connections to national collaborators.

3.3. Adapting terminology: citizen-driven vs change-driven initiative

The assessment provides insights for each CDI and thus gives substantial information about the structure and the different driving forces behind each organisation. During the Task 3.1 as part of WP3 work, the Steering Group as well as the respective CDI partners agreed to change the acronym of CDI to change-driven initiatives. The synthesis of each CDI provides the justification that the CDIs are operating as ambassadors for transformative change but are not necessarily directly run or driven by the citizens themselves.

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Appendices

Appendix 1. Project kick-off agenda

DAY 1 - 20 September 2022	
11.00	<i>Pre-meeting (Work Package Leaders and Coordinator team only)</i>
12.00	Get-together Lunch & coffee
13.00	Welcome by Coordinator Interactive round of introduction <i>Each participant (1-2min): Bring your (food) item that symbols for your expectation and/or personal driver why you are part of the FOSTER team – Let us know!</i>
14.00h	About FOSTER - our approach, vision and ambition <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overall project structure, FOSTER approach of integration of reflection and learning dynamics (WP 6 - Kerstin Pasch, Anne Loeber) • Available and accessible knowledge about food systems in EU (WP1 - Kerstin Cuhls) • Food system education system in Europe (WP2 - John Ingram) • Citizen engagement & Citizen Driven Initiatives (WP3 - Klaus Hadwiger, <i>n.n. one person per Citizen Driven Initiative CDI</i>)
15.45	<i>Coffee Break and CDI posters session (one poster per CDI)</i>
16.30	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Food systems considerations on EU (national) R&I level (Thom Achterbosch) • Dissemination & Communication in FOSTER (Douglas Thompson) • Citizen science & food systems (Enrico Maria Balli)
17.30	General Assembly (Kerstin Pasch) - Operational procedures for the General Assembly - Legal and finance issues - Project communication (DIL sharepoint) - Project meetings
17.45	End of presentations DAY 1
17.45	Reflection session (Only for Work Package Leaders and Coordination Team)
19.00	Walking tour & Aperero, and Dinner Meeting point (19h): Royal Palace of Brussels, Place des Palais 7, 1000 Brussels Dinner (21h): Restaurant Vincent, Rue des Dominicains 8, 1000 Bruxelles

DAY 2 - 21 September 2022	
8.30	<p>Interactive Sessions in parallel working groups</p> <p>Round 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing the FOSTER Platform (lead by Kerstin Cuhls) • Implement citizen science strategies and engage Citizen Driven Initiatives (lead by Klaus Hadwiger)
9.15	<i>Coffee break</i>
10.00	<p>Round 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explore the FOSTER Academy (lead by John Ingram) • Reorienting R&I governance towards FOKIS (Food System Knowledge and Innovation System, lead by Thom Achterbosch)
10.45	<i>Coffee break</i>
11.00	<p>Round 3</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dissemination, exploitation and sustainability (lead by Douglas Thompson) • Scaling out and deep FOSTER CDIs to communities (lead by Enrico Maria Balli)
11.45	Results of Interactive Session by session leaders
12.15	<p>FOSTER policy & project implementation> Astrid Guiffart REA (project officer) and Giulia Meloni DG RTD (policy officer)</p>
12.45	Wrap up session and next steps (Kerstin Pasch and Anne Loeber)
13.00	End of Kick-off Meeting
13.00	Lunch
14.00-15.00	<p>Reflection session (Work Package Leaders and Coordination Team only)</p>

Appendix 2. Survey: baseline assessment of the CDI

FOSTER-Project -Baseline Assessment of the Citizen Driven Initiative (CDI)

Basic Structure of the Citizen Driven Initiative (CDI)	
Question	Remarks
1, Name of the CDI	national language/english translation
2, Has the CDI a business office?	e.g. how big is the office, is the location freely accessible and usable etc.
3, Brief description of the history of the initiative	e.g. when founded, by whom, what led to the foundation etc.
4, What is the formal objective of the CDI?	e.g. mission, overall objective etc.
5, Company/Corporate form of the initiative?	e.g. Association, Club, Society, NGO, NPO, Council, SME etc.
6, Numbers of employees?	e.g. full or part time employees
7, Numbers of formal members?	e.g. membership applications, membership fees, membership work service etc.
8, Numbers of involved volunteers?	e.g. could differ within project and activities
9, Management structure	e.g. elected board, CEO etc.

FOSTER-Project -Baseline Assessment of the Citizen Driven Initiative (CDI)

Networks and Relationships of the Citizen Driven Initiative (CDI)	
Question	Remarks
10, Which stakeholders are involved in the CDI?	e.g. local farmers, concerned citizens etc.
1.	
11, Does the initiative accompany political processes?	e.g. hearings in political decision-making bodies
12, Is the initiative part of a network?	e.g. what kind of network, are there cooperations with other initiatives for specific activities etc.
13, Is there a timeframe for this network?	e.g. temporary, longevity is targeted etc.
14, What is spatial reach of the initiative?	e.g. local, regional, national, european
Financing Structure of the Citizen Driven Initiative (CDI)	
Question	Remarks
15, How is the CDI financed?	e.g. third-party funding, government subsidies etc.
16, Are there membership fees in your CDI?	How much does a membership cost, are the fees income-dependent?
17, Absolute proportions of the respective financing sources?	e.g. fundings, subsidies, fees etc.
18, Available budget of the CDI per year?	specification of a range if not constant annually (min./max)

Appendix 3. Focus group guiding questions.

Focus group 1, KP+CDIs

Introduction part

- Welcome participants, small ice-breaker
- Aim of the focus group:
 1. To solicit and deeply understand CDIs claims, concerns and issues from within their own worldview and rationale.
 2. Create the research steps adopted for the particular case studies.
 3. To support the ongoing relationship-building between the KP+CDIs and beyond.
- Who is part of the Focus Group?

The objective is to cover ALL themes, but the detail of questions depends per case study.

**Note: please make sure to always clarify whose needs/gaps are being discussed, e.g. the respective CDI and/or the other parties (stakeholders) they work with (work for). **Transcripts + summary made by the KP.*

Theme	Main questions (PRIORITY 1)	Follow up (PRIORITY 2)
Visions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What is your vision as a CDI (long, short term), and is it written down in your official statutes? How often is this vision re-evaluated with the stakeholders? 2. How do you see your role(s) in achieving this/these vision(s)? 3. How does that role / do these roles complement the ambitions of FOSTER: producing an impact in terms of food system transformation / knowledge system transformation, enabling public engagement? 4. In which way do you decide on your work programme, driven by whom, which are the other needs that have to be considered – are other actor needs and objectives part of your objectives? 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. To what extent are the visions of the actors you collaborate with integrated in your work/goals/objectives? 2. What are your next steps in achieving your vision(s)?
General needs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What issues ('needs') do you come across for achieving the vision(s)? 	<i>Mapping exercise with post-its (10 min silence to gather thoughts and write them down, silent wall) for</i>

(important for all)		<i>this section – general needs. No reflection at this moment on each post-it.</i>
Public engagement	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What actors (partners) are you working with now? And to what extent do you integrate the actor (partner) needs in your vision(s)? 2. What actors are you still missing in your network? What challenges do you experience while building the network? 3. To what extent is your initiative including underrepresented groups? Are there any needs/gaps in this respect? 4. What role do citizens play in your initiative? How do you make sure that the needs of citizens are considered in decision-making? 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>How do you ensure being transparent in your activities? Are there any needs/gaps in this respect?</i> 2. <i>What is your foreseen impact on these actors by their involvement in your work?</i> 3. <i>How do you reflect on power relations in your CDI / in your contact with other actors?</i>
Knowledge & Innovation System	<p>How do you define Knowledge & Innovation System?</p> <p>What Knowledge & Innovation activities are you currently engaged in? What would you need to play a bigger role in the Knowledge & Innovation System for food?</p> <p>Receiving knowledge & training</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What knowledge, skills and activities do you need for your activities and to further your objectives? 2. What types of knowledge do you work with and who provides you with it? 3. Do you have access to the knowledge and skills you need? 4. Does the current Knowledge & Innovation System align with your needs for information, expertise and practical skills and in what way does it/ does it not? Needs/gaps. <p>Producing/creating knowledge & innovation</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. What knowledge and skills does your initiative create? Do you experience any barriers/resistance in this respect? 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Are the knowledge and skills you create publicly available? How do you do make them public?</i> 2. <i>(referring to question 1 in receiving knowledge and training) How can FOSTER support you in this?</i> 3. <i>In what way you would like to be involved in Knowledge & Innovation activities and how would you like to be supported (e.g. government, research institutes, private organizations, NGOs, etc)?</i> 4. <i>Via what stakeholders can you learn about Knowledge & Innovation system?</i>

	6. How do you see your role in collaboration and in knowledge transfer?	
Governance	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How are you working with other stakeholders? And how do you organise this work? How do you organize this collaboration? 2. How do these arrangements provide you with access to knowledge and skills? 3. What are the reasons for the cooperations mentioned above? Have you experienced any barriers in these cooperations, if so – please, elaborate. 4. Are you connected with policy makers, and if so, how? If not, why not? Have you experienced any barriers in these cooperations, if so – please, elaborate. 5. What is the impact of policy on the scope and organisation of your activities? 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Are there any other important stakeholders you wish to collaborate with to further your objectives, via networks/collaborations/organizations?</i> 2. <i>What formal agreements have you made with the policy makers?</i>
Food system	1. What are the needs/gaps/barriers in food system from your perspective – and how is this reflected in your vision?	1. <i>How do you “define” food system (see the template if needed for confirmation)?</i>
	<i>Needs and gaps beyond those sections listed above, including looking at the post its from the beginning – what has been discussed, what hasn't been discussed.</i>	

Closing part

Wrapping up, collecting post-its if anything useful is there – were there any needs written down that did not get addressed?

? Discussing who the CDIs would like to invite (external collaborators) for the second focus group?

Thanking the participants for their participation 😊

Appendix 4. Slides of the focus group training.

CHECK - IN

How are you?

How do you feel about the focus groups?

FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSION

What is the difference to individual interviews?

Accumulation of Discussion

Includes different perspectives

People can react to what others say

Participants get a common understanding of what is being discussed

FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSION

Mindset

Curious listener

Listening to understand

Opportunity creator for discussion

Have fun

FOCUS GROUP SET UP

- Minimum 3 participants
- Circle -> possible to see people
- Quiet Room, possibly at CDI

Circle --> everyone sees everyone

FOCUS GROUP SET UP

- One discussion leader, one documenting
- Note taking
- One Microphone, ideally two

I will lead the discussion, Julia is documenting the process

SETTING THE TONE

- Arrive early, welcome people individually
- Snacks and Drinks
- Share appreciation and intention of the meeting
- Check-in

First 15 minutes
What's your name and role in CDI?
What motivates you to be part of the CDI?

THANK YOU

GOING THROUGH TOPICS

- Start with naming the broad topics
- Ask starting question and let them discuss
- Check if the points were (almost) covered
- Summarise and name next topic

Today we have 5 different topics. We will start with...

STEERING THE DISCUSSION

- Would you agree with this?
- Does anyone have a different opinion?
- From your perspective is it different?
- Can you tell me more?
- What is your experience in this field?
- From all of the things you said... what would be your top priority?
- I have not heard from you in a while, what is your opinion about this?

- watch peoples reactions
- try to make sure to include everyone
- participants don't have to agree
- try to create breaks to think

TIPS

- Decide on a time that suits people with different roles in the organisation and different needs.
- Read the information that we have about CDI *beforehand*
- Time keeping
- if you don't understand something now, it will very likely not be clearer on the recording

FOCUS GROUP 1 CDI INTERNAL	FOCUS GROUP 2 CDI COLLABORATORS
<p>minimum 3 participants</p> <p>Needs, Gaps, Barriers for CDI Vision. For things they want to achieve.</p> <p>2h Should take place in May</p> <p>Benefit: Have a common understanding</p>	<p>minimum 1 CDI person, minimum 3 collaborators</p> <p>Needs, Gaps, Barriers for their united food system transformation</p> <p>Same questions different perspective</p> <p>2h Should take place in June</p> <p>Benefit: Understand the needs of their stakeholders, partners.</p>

